

Nickel(II) mixed chelates with Dibasic ONO Schiff Bases and $\alpha\alpha'$ -Dipyridyl (or *o*-Phenanthroline)

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IN this communication we describe the syntheses and properties of nickel(II) mixed chelates $[\text{Ni}(\text{L})(\text{dipy}/o\text{-phen})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ where LH_2 stands for a molecule of a tridentate dibasic ONO Schiff base derived from the condensation of salicylaldehyde and an amino acid like glycine, *dl*- α -alanine, β -alanine, *dl*-valine, *L*-leucine etc.

The ethanol insoluble, light blue violet coloured nickel(II) Schiff base complex, $[\text{Ni}(\text{LH})_2]^1$ ($\text{LH}_2 = \text{salicylidene-glycine}$) (.0025*M*) reacts in refluxing ethanol with dipyridyl/*o*-phenanthroline (.0025*M*) to produce a green solution from which green, hydrated $[\text{Ni}(\text{L})(\text{dipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]/[\text{Ni}(\text{L})(o\text{-phen})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ has been isolated (Method A). Second route involves reaction of nickel chloride hexahydrate (.002*M*) with glycine (.002*M*), salicylaldehyde (sal H) (.002*M*) and anhydrous sodium acetate in alcohol, being followed by the addition of dipyridyl/*o*-phenanthroline (.002*M*) (Method B). A third method consists of reacting in ethanol green coloured $[\text{Ni}(\text{sal})_2(\text{dipy}/o\text{-phen})]$ (.002*M*) with the amino acid (.002*M*) (Method C). In a fourth method we have utilised interaction of light blue coloured $[\text{Ni}(\text{gly})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^2$ (glyH = glycine) (.002*M*) with salH (.002*M*) in ethanol being followed by the addition of dipyridyl/*o*-phenanthroline (.002*M*) (Method D). Characterisation data of a few representative mixed chelates only are shown in Table 1.

Coordination of a tridentate and a bidentate ligand around nickel(II) should generate a five coordinate geometry. However, in all of our products there are a number of water molecules, one of which cannot be removed even after prolonged heating at 120°. This last can only be removed under vacuum in a drying pistol over boiling xylene at 140°, the colour changing from green to yellow brown. It is believed that this last water molecule completes a pseudo octahedral geometry around nickel(II). In keeping with this contention all the complexes are light green and give typical spectra for six coordinate $[\text{NiN}_3\text{O}_3]$ chromophore. For example, the first and second transitions in $[\text{Ni}(\text{L})(\text{dipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ occur at: ν_1 , 11.24 kK ($\epsilon = 18$; ethanol) and ν_2 , 17.54 kK ($\epsilon = 13.4$; ethanol). The low molar extinction coefficients are usual for pseudo octahedral geometry³. These two transitions are assigned ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(\text{F})$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(\text{F})$ respectively. The third transition ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(\text{P})$ is swamped by the intense bands of dipyridyl/*o*-phenanthroline. The 10 Dq (11.24 kK) is consistent with the average ligand field strength and positions of the ligands in the spectrochemical series (cf: 10 Dq of $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+}$, 8.5 kK; $[\text{Ni}(\text{en})_3]^{2+}$, 11.5 kK; $[\text{Ni}(\text{dipy})_3]^{2+}$, 12.6 kK)³. The ν_2/ν_1 (Table 2) of the mixed chelates is ~ 1.54 which is also typical of six coordinate geometry about nickel(II)⁴. The magnetic moments (Table 2) are also normal for the proposed geometry⁴. Conductivity data in methanol rule out alternative ionic formulation such as $[\text{Ni}(\text{dipy})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2][\text{NiL}_2]$.

A number of Schiff bases are currently under study. The response of these complexes to a considerable excess of dipyridyl/*o*-phenanthroline is being examined with a view to expose any flexidentate character of the schiff bases. Details of all these studies will be published in due course.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF $[\text{Ni}(\text{L})(\text{DIPY}/o\text{-PHEN})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ (COMPOUNDS WERE DRIED AT 110° BEFORE ANALYSIS).

LH ₂	dipy/ o-phen	Method	Colour	% Ni		% N		% H ₂ O (by loss at 140° under vacuum)	
				Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Salicylidene-glycine	dipy	A	light green	14.32	14.32	10.30	10.25	3.38	4.39
		B		14.14	14.32	10.28	10.25		
		C		14.48	14.32	10.10	10.25		
		D		14.10	14.32	10.35	10.25		
Salicylidene-glycine	o-phen	A	light green	13.32	13.50	8.90	9.68	4.29	4.15
		B		13.18	13.50	9.67	9.68		
Salicylidene- <i>dl</i> - α -alanine.	dipy	A	light green	13.58	13.86	9.81	9.91	3.82	4.25
		C		13.70	13.86	9.74	9.91		

TABLE 2—CONDUCTIVITY, MAGNETIC MOMENT AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF $[\text{Ni}(\text{L})(\text{DIPY}/o\text{-PHEN})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$

LH ₂	dipy/ o-phen	Conductivity in methanol ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹	Magnetic moment B.M.	Spectra in ethanol kK (mole.extn.coeff.).		
				ν_1	ν_2	$\nu_2 : \nu_1$
Salicylidene-glycine	dipy	2	3.23	11.24(18.2)	17.54(13.4)	1.56
Salicylidene-glycine	o-phen	7	3.14	11.24(19.6)	17.54(12.1)	1.56
Salicylidene- <i>dl</i> - α -alanine	dipy	3	3.14	11.49(18.4)	17.54(13.2)	1.52

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Thiocyanato and Cyanato Complexes of Copper(II) and Nickel(II) with 1,3-Diaminopropane-2-ol, $H_2NCH_2CH(OH)CH_2NH_2$

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In recent years much interest has been shown on the transition metal complexes of ambidentate ligands. Owing to its ambidentate nature, the pseudohalides and host of other ligands of similar properties, can show the phenomena of linkage isomerisms in coordination complexes.¹ In this note we describe the preparation and properties of some thiocyanato- and cyanato complexes of nickel(II) and copper(II) with 1,3-diaminopropane-2-ol (= L). This work is an extension of our previous study on the coordination complexes of copper(II), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) salts (including pseudohalides) with neutral Schiff bases^{2,3} and pyrazoles.⁴

Experimental

(All the preparations were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere).

$Cu(L)_2(SCN)_2$, (I): An ethanolic solution of cupric nitrate trihydrate (0.005 mole) was refluxed for 15 min in presence of 20 ml of 2,2-dimethoxypropane. To this refluxed solution was then added L (0.01 mole) in 10 ml of ethanol, followed by the addition of solid ammonium thiocyanate (0.01 mole). The whole mixture was then refluxed for 10 min, and the dark blue solution was filtered. The filtrate on slow evaporation in a vacuum desiccator yielded blue crystals. These were filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol, ether and then dried in a desiccator over anhydrous $CaCl_2$.

The complex is soluble in pyridine, dimethylsulfoxide and dimethylformamide. The compound is paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 1.90$ B.M. at 29°). Found: SCN, 32.06; Cu, 17.85%. Calc. for $C_8H_{20}N_6O_2S_2Cu$: SCN, 32.27; Cu, 17.66%.

$Cu(L)_2(NCO)_2$, (II): Analogous method by using potassium cyanate instead of ammonium thiocyanate yielded this bluish green crystals.

The compound is paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 1.88$ B.M. at 28°). Found: N, 25.14; Cu, 19.71%. Calc. for $C_8H_{20}N_6O_4Cu$: N, 25.65; Cu, 19.39%.

$Ni(L)_2(SCN)_2$, (III): Following the method of analogous copper(II) complexes and using nickel nitrate hexahydrate instead of copper(II) nitrate trihydrate, this pale green complex was isolated.

It is paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 3.22$ B.M. at 28°). Found: SCN, 32.19; Ni, 16.14%. Calc. for $C_8H_{20}N_6O_2S_2Ni$: SCN, 32.68; Ni, 16.63%.

$Ni(L)_2(NCO)_2$, (IV): Following the method used for corresponding copper(II) complex, this pale green complex was isolated.

It is paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 3.35$ B.M. at 28°). Found: N, 25.71; Ni, 18.02%. Calc. for $C_8H_{20}N_6O_4Ni$: N, 26.01; Ni, 18.27%.

Results and Discussion

The copper(II) complexes $Cu(L)_2(SCN)_2$, (I) and $Cu(L)_2(NCO)_2$, (II) are sufficiently stable to handle in the atmospheric conditions. These two complexes are highly soluble in pyridine and DMSO, and in the latter solvent they are found to be virtually non-conducting (Λ_M varies between 2.8–3.5 mhos of a $\times 10^{-3}M$ solution at room temperature). The magnetic moments are calculated to be 1.90 and 1.88 B.M. (room temperature) respectively, which suggest the presence of one unpaired electron as expected for a d^9 system. The i.r. spectral data (Table) support that the anions SCN and NCO are coordinated to the metal ion, which is in conformity with the non-conducting nature of the chelates.

The i.r. spectra of the two copper complexes exhibit two bands at 2080 cm^{-1} (s) and 720 cm^{-1} (m) in the regions of ν_{C-N} and ν_{C-S} vibrations respectively, which is diagnostic for S-bonded SCN ligand.⁵ It has been suggested by Tramer⁶ that on coordination, the high frequency $C \equiv N$ stretching mode is raised by $\sim 30-40$ cm^{-1} , $\sim 50-70$ cm^{-1} and 70–120 cm^{-1} over the ν_{C-N} band observed at 1963 cm^{-1} for the ionic thiocyanate group indicating terminal N- and S- and bridging thiocyanate group respectively. However, the ν_{C-S} stretching frequency which drops in S-bonded thiocyanate complexes⁷ relative to that in KSCN, (ν_{C-S} at 749 cm^{-1}) can be a more useful guide to the mode of thiocyanate bonding. In the present case, its occurrence at 720 cm^{-1} clearly indicates the S-bonding.

TABLE—INFRARED AND VISIBLE ABSORPTION SPECTRAL DATA (CM^{-1}) OF $Cu(II)$ AND $Ni(II)$ COMPLEXES

Complex	ν_{C-N}	ν_{C-S}	ν_{C-O}	ν_{max} (nujol mull)
$Cu(L)_2(SCN)_2$, (I)	2080(s)	720(m)	—	16,600
$Cu(L)_2(NCO)_2$, (II)	2135(s)	—	1338(m)	16,800
$Ni(L)_2(SCN)_2$, (III)	2078(s)	730(m)	—	10,850; 12,850(sh); 16,950.
$Ni(L)_2(NCO)_2$, (IV)	2130(m)	—	1330(m)	10,500; 13,000(sh); 16,800.